

Case Study

Assessing the Impact of Landslides on the Right to Life and Livelihood: A Study of the Chittagong Metropolitan Area

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ABSTRACT

Landslides are among the most dangerous disasters in Bangladesh's hilly areas. Additionally, landslides cause significant damage where they occur, including economic losses, infrastructure damage, loss of life, hindrance to the education system, violation of the right to livelihood, and damage to the transportation system. Landslides create a violation of human rights, especially the right to life and the right to livelihood of poor people who live on hill slopes due to a lack of accommodation. Article 15(a) of the Bangladesh Constitution mentions that it shall be a fundamental duty of the state to secure to the citizens the necessities of life, including food, clothing, shelter, education, and medical care. However, human rights protection of disaster victims also needs to be provided in these contexts. Currently, policies lack specific provisions for timely aid and legal protections for vulnerable groups. The objective of the study is to evaluate whether the disaster relief mechanism supports a human rights approach by analyzing existing policies and proposing reforms, such as establishing enforceable rights for disaster victims and integrating human rights standards into disaster management frameworks. Lastly, it investigates whether national policy is sufficient to reduce risk and harm. This paper has followed a qualitative methodology and a comprehensive conceptual and theoretical structure, with the key concern being the human rights gap in disaster relief. Furthermore, neglecting the human rights of the victims, severely affected by natural disasters, means overlooking the fact that such people do not live in a legal framework. The paper identifies loopholes in the existing legal framework and offers durable recommendations for the sustainable conservation of disaster victims in Bangladesh.

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Introduction

A landslide is a geological event encompassing a wide range of ground movements, including rock falls, deep-slope failure, and shallow debris flows (Rahman, 2012). The Chittagong city corporation area is highly vulnerable to landslide hazards. Landslides were not considered a major disaster threat in Chittagong before (Ahmed et al., 2022). However, it has been considered a major disaster in Chittagong since 2007. A landslide caused enormous damage in 2007 due to heavy rain in June (Abedin et al., 2020; Kamal et al., 2022; Saha et al., 2005; Schuster & Highland, 2003). This research intends to explore the diverse and disproportionate vulnerabilities of landslides and their impacts on people. Earlier research has primarily focused on the causes of landslides; however, no such extensive research has been found on the human rights violations resulting from the cascading impacts of landslides in Chittagong.

The specific objectives are:

- a. To explore the vulnerability of people due to the increased frequency and intensity of landslides.
- b. To understand the challenges people face in Chittagong due to the continued impacts of landslides.
- c. To address the human rights gaps in disaster relief for the affected people.
- d. To evaluate the adequacy of existing legal frameworks addressing hill cutting and landslides in Bangladesh.

This paper further aims to identify whether the successful implementation of disaster laws is often linked to communities being well-informed, engaged, and resourced to take an active part in reducing risks in a country. With this in mind, this paper aims to review existing national-level legal mechanisms for victims of disasters to seek justice and to examine the extent to which accountability is open to potential victims. Moreover, this paper will review the international system to observe whether international human rights monitoring mechanisms, in particular, can hold States accountable for their underperformance in disaster situations.

Research Methodology

The study adopted a qualitative methodology to address the objectives outlined above. Both primary and secondary data have been used for the study. The primary data were collected from residents of three locations of Chittagong City (Batali Hill, Moti Jharna, and Tiger Pass) through direct interviews. We collected data from 50 respondents in the risky, hilly areas of the Chittagong Metropolitan Area. A questionnaire was prepared in line with the study's objectives. In addition, various research findings were used as secondary sources. Moreover, various published materials have been considered in developing the study's theoretical framework. In the Moti Jharna area, we arranged a focus group discussion. The residents were gathered in a place and participated in a focus group discussion. They shared their experiences. The data collected from the participants are used in this paper, in accordance with the research guidelines, to address the consequences of the landslides. A socio-legal approach has been maintained towards the research problem; an attempt was made to understand and evaluate the

legal findings in the context of the socio-economic reality. Apart from this, the existing government policy framework on hill cutting was also discussed analytically. A wide range of literature reviews was also conducted to understand the causes, consequences, and human rights impacts of landslides.

Vulnerabilities of Landslides in the Chittagong Metropolitan Area

Landslide is a geologic hazard in Bangladesh, especially in Chittagong and the southeastern part of the country.¹ In recent years, the scenario of the landslide occurrences has crossed all previous records.² It has caused death to more than 300 people in Bangladesh since 2000, with a loss of hundreds of houses and millions of dollars of property. In the Chittagong Hill Tracts, about 152 people died on 13th June 2017. On 11th June 2007, about 127 people died in Chittagong city. The Chittagong City Corporation area is highly prone to landslide hazards.³ All the major landslide events occurred due to much higher rainfall. Moreover, rapid urbanization, increased population density, improper land use, and alterations in the hilly regions by illegally cutting the hills, indiscriminate deforestation, and agricultural practices aggravate the landslide vulnerability in the Chittagong city area.⁴ Here, low-income people live near or under the hill by risking their own lives.⁵ Natural disasters affect the vulnerable sector of the population.⁶

In Chittagong city, landslide vulnerability and climate variability are more severe in Batali Hill than in Moti Jharna, according to the survey (Kabir & Mahmud, 2021). It was also found from the survey that many houses have been damaged and domestic animals have died in the landslides. Also, the roads are blocked, and transportation is hampered. Many families were displaced from their houses, and they were forced to take shelter in another safe location; some families were permanently displaced. Findings from field interviews with 50 respondents and a focus group discussion show that the vulnerabilities to landslides in Chittagong occur due to socio-economic marginalization, environmental degradation, and governance failures. Participants believe unplanned hill-cutting, deforestation, and unauthorized housing on steep slopes are crucial factors. Respondents from informal settlements in areas such as Batali Hill, Moti Jharna, and Tiger Pass mentioned how poverty compels families to inhabit hazardous hilly slopes despite knowing the risks (Kabir & Mahmud, 2021). Some of them also informed that relocation to safer areas is impossible due to financial restraints. This shows vulnerability not as a mere environmental condition, but as a manifestation of structural inequality. The focus group discussion also revealed that disaster preparedness and early warning mechanisms are

¹ Sarwar G.M., Landslide Tragedy of Bangladesh, Paper presented at the First World Landslide Forum, United Nations University (UNU), Tokyo, Japan (2008)

² Mahmood A.B. and Khan M.H., Landslide Vulnerability of Bangladesh Hills and of 2007, Landslide in Chittagong City: SAARC Workshop on Landslide, Risk Management in South Asia, 62-68 (2010)

³ Mahmood A.B. and Khan M.H., Landslide vulnerability of Bangladesh Hills and sustainable Management options: A case study of 2007 Landslide in Chittagong City, Proceedings: International Seminar on Management and Mitigation of Water-induced Disasters, 21-22 April 2008, Kathmandu, 112-123 (2008)

⁴ Bayas A. and Yiasen R.R., MyCOE/SERVIR Himalayas Fellowship Program, Understanding the issues involved in urban landslide vulnerability in Chittagong metropolitan area, Bangladesh, ICIMOD, Available at <https://sites.google.com/a/aag.org/mycoe> (2013)

⁵ Islam M.N. and Uddin M.N., Country paper on hydrogeology section, In International workshop on arsenic issue in Bangladesh, Dhaka (2002)

⁶ M. Bizzarri, 'Protection of Vulnerable Groups in Natural and Man-Made Disasters', in A. de Guttery, M. Gestri and G. Venturini (eds.), *International Disaster Response Law* 381 (2012), at 386-389; N. Zack, *Ethics for Disaster* (2009), at 108.

not adequately monitored. Several respondents said that after previous landslide incidents, immediate relief was provided, but long-term rehabilitation or compensation has not been provided yet.

Theoretical Framework: Human Rights-Based Approach

Human rights are those rights that are inherent to all human beings. All human beings, regardless of nationality, place of residence, sex, national or ethnic origin, color, religion, language, or any other status, deserve dignity, which is protected through the idea of human rights (Universal Declaration of Human Rights, 1948). As proclaimed by the UN General Assembly in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights adopted on 10 December 1948, this is a common standard for all peoples and all nations. Human rights cover civil and political rights, such as the right to life, equality before the law, and freedom of expression; economic, social, and cultural rights, such as the rights to work, social security, and education; and collective rights, such as the right to development and self-determination of peoples.⁷

Therefore, rights-based approaches are mechanisms that ensure the realization and safeguarding of human rights.⁸ Human beings as right-holders can demand rights from duty-bearers for their fulfillment. The State, as the main duty-bearer, by adopting international human rights law, possesses both the moral and legal obligation to respect, protect, facilitate, and fulfill human rights.⁹ A human rights-based approach leads to greater accountability and empowerment of those involved in the disaster management process. A State should be accountable for its actions, and there should be an effective mechanism that includes specific measures to ensure that States' obligations are carried out in these national emergencies (Amaratunga et al., 2019). At the same time, people should be empowered to claim their rights. This approach proposes that people should have knowledge of their human rights. They should be able to individually or collectively take actions to fully realize their rights.¹⁰

From a human rights perspective, States, as the main duty-bearers, have the primary duty and responsibility to assist persons affected by natural disasters for the protection of their human rights.¹¹ States have the duty to provide at least the bare minimum of food, water, clothing, shelter, and health services necessary for the survival of the affected population. If these minimum core obligations, for example, under the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights,¹² are not fulfilled, a state party to this treaty may be found in violation of some of its human rights obligations. States can also be responsible for violations of human

⁷ See un-Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights website, <http://www.ohchr.org/en/issues/Pages/WhatareHumanRights.aspx> (last accessed 6 November 2025).

⁸ Anders Dahlbeck, a human rights-based approach to the means of implementation of the sustainable development goals, published by The Danish Institute for Human Rights, 2021

⁹ U. Jonsson, 'Human Rights Approach to Development Programming', UNICEF United Nations Children's Fund, Eastern and Southern Africa Regional Office, April 2003.

¹⁰ See N 13

¹¹ Brookings-Bern Project on Internal Displacement, 'Human Rights and Natural Disasters. Operational Guidelines and Field Manual on Human Rights Protection in Situations of Natural Disaster,' March 2008, <http://www.refworld.org/docid/49a2b8f72.html> (last accessed 03 December 2024).

¹² 1966 International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, 993 unts 3 (icescr).

rights by not engaging in disaster risk reduction, which, if undertaken, could have prevented the occurrence of a disaster.¹³

Addressing the Human Rights Gap in Disaster Relief

In Bangladesh, the human rights of disaster victims are not sufficiently taken into consideration. As a result, it generates unequal access to assistance, discrimination in aid distribution, enforced relocation, sexual and gender-based violence, and loss of documentation.¹⁴ These problems are often encountered by the affected people. These violations could be avoided if both national and international actors took the relevant human rights guarantees into account from the beginning through sustainable disaster relief. Missions and evaluations by the Representative of the UN Secretary-General (RSG) on the human rights of internally displaced persons show that not only are national authorities often unaware of the relevance of human rights norms in the context of natural disasters, but also International agencies and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) are not successful in incorporating a human rights-based approach into emergency relief and response, even though many of the laws and codes of conduct applicable in situations of natural disaster contain such guarantees. Furthermore, neglecting the human rights of those affected by natural disasters overlooks the fact that they do not live in a legal vacuum. However, countries with laws, rules, and institutions should protect their rights.

The current Disaster Management Framework in Bangladesh

Managing disaster risk reduction and climate change adaptation remains a daunting task, as it encompasses efforts to reduce poverty, increase resilience, improve resource management, and mitigate the impacts of disasters. However, the government has made rapid progress in improving the disaster management infrastructure lately. Unlike many other countries, Bangladesh has made impressive progress in recognizing the linkages between development and disasters across its key legislative, policy, and development planning frameworks. An assessment of national adaptation planning highlights Bangladesh's Vision 2021 as a key document for leveraging climate change as a core guiding vision/plan, supported by the Ministry of Environment and Forestry (Zamudio & Parry, 2016). This is supported by various policies and action plans, including the National Adaptation Program of Action (NAPA) (Fatemi, Okyere, Diko, & Kita, 2020). Bangladesh has also established a robust foundation for efficient and impactful disaster governance. The legal framework is founded on the Disaster Management Act, Standing Orders on Disasters, and the National Plans for Disaster Management (NPDM), which are further supported by various other plans drafted for specific purposes at the sub-national level. The Bangladesh Climate Change Trust Fund, funded entirely by the government, aims to strengthen national capacity to cope with climate change impacts, guided by the Bangladesh Climate Change Strategy and Action Plan (BCCSAP) 2009. Under it, several projects have been implemented to strengthen infrastructure resilience (Ministry of Finance, 2014). The Climate Change Resilience Fund serves as a financial mechanism that allocates 10 percent of its funding to civil society and private-sector projects, with funds

¹³ F. Rawinji, 'Claiming the Human Right to Protection from Disasters: The Case for Human Rights-based Disaster Risk Reduction', http://www.preventionweb.net/files/submissions/31225_righttodisasterprotection.pdf (last accessed 26 November 2024).

¹⁴ LEWIS B, MAGUIRE R. A Human Rights-based Approach to Disaster Displacement in the Asia-Pacific. *Asian Journal of International Law*. 2016;6(2):326-352. doi:10.1017/S2044251315000168

directly supporting community resilience through research and climate-resilient planning (Khan, Huq, & Shamsuddoha, 2018).

To maintain an understanding of disaster risks, gathering and analyzing data on vulnerabilities, exposure, and hazards is necessary for conducting risk assessments, prioritizing investments, and improving the capacity to issue timely and appropriate early warnings. The Dhaka Water Supply and Sewerage Authority (WASA), the Directorate of Land Records and Surveys (DLRS), the Bangladesh Forest Department (BFD), the Soil Resource Development Institute (SRDI), and the Agriculture Research Center (BARC) are among the organizations that maintain it.

Despite institutional mechanisms aimed at improving proactive disaster risk management, challenges remain. Alongside social challenges, issues related to financing, capacity, coordination, and accountability persist.

A Human Rights-Based Approach to Disaster Relief

Protection means securing the survival and physical security of those affected by natural disasters. They can be civil and political as well as economic, social, and cultural rights. Although all human rights are fundamentally interrelated, for practical reasons, these rights can be divided into four groups, namely:

- A. rights related to physical security and integrity (such as protection of the right to life and the right to be free from assault, rape, arbitrary detention, kidnapping, and threats concerning the above);
- B. rights related to the basic necessities of life (such as the rights to food, drinking water, shelter, adequate clothing, adequate health services, and sanitation);
- C. rights related to other economic, social, and cultural protection needs (such as the rights to have access to education and work as well as to receive restitution or compensation for lost property); and
- D. rights related to other civil and political protection needs (such as the rights to religious freedom and freedom of speech, personal documentation, political participation, access to courts, and freedom from discrimination).

The primary responsibility for providing such protection and assistance during emergencies lies with the national authorities of the affected countries. Victims have the right to request and receive protection and assistance from their governments. States, therefore, have an obligation to do everything within their power to prevent and mitigate the potential negative consequences of landslides. UN agencies, international and national NGOs, and other relevant international actors play a crucial role in advocating for victims' rights. Furthermore, they can assist governments in improving their national capacity to protect rights. Where national capacity is insufficient, the international community needs to support and supplement the efforts of the government and local authorities.

Strengthening Accountability through International and National Mechanisms

Although international human rights law does not clearly spell out a right to protection and relief from disasters, the combined analysis of various provisions of international human rights

law suggests that this is implied.¹⁵ A natural hazard may lead to a disaster that negatively affects the enjoyment of various human rights, such as the right to life, property, and livelihoods.¹⁶ International human rights monitoring bodies do not pay particular regard to natural disasters. However, to the extent that human rights issues are related to natural disasters, the topic may increasingly gain space in the practice of these bodies.

The practice of the UN Human Rights Committee, the UN treaty body, is mandated with the monitoring of States' compliance with their obligations under the ICCPR.¹⁷ It has not yet been clearly articulated that States have an obligation to protect the right to life of persons likely to be affected by natural disasters, but it has also not been suggested to the contrary either. In relation to economic, social, and cultural rights, the practice of the UN Committee on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights can be monitored in such situations. This practice revealed very few instances in which human rights were linked to natural disasters. For example, in 2010, the CESCR indicated its appreciation of the positive role played by the Dominican Republic in response to the Haitian earthquake, although it did not further elaborate on this.¹⁸ From this discussion, one may get the general impression that international procedures are relatively few and their effectiveness is not undisputed.

It seems that respect for human rights and community participation could enhance disaster risk reduction efforts, and thus reduce the need for victims to seek post-disaster justice. The right to take part in the public affairs of the State, based on Article 25 ICCPR, should be appreciated. The Human Rights Committee interpreted this article, suggesting that individuals should also participate in public policies, such as disaster-related policies that affect them.¹⁹

In Bangladesh, the legal basis for preventing illegal hill cutting is the Building Construction Act, which was enacted in 1952 with a view to preventing haphazard erection of buildings, excavation of tanks, and cutting of hills and hillocks in Bangladesh (Ahmed et al., 2022). But later on, the government amended the 1952 Act twice in 1987 and in 1990 (Rahman, 2012). By amendment, sections 3C and 3D were inserted into the 1952 Act. According to 3C of the Act, no person is allowed, without the previous sanction of the authorized officer, to cut or raze any hill. As per this section, no such sanction should be provided unless the authorized officer or such officer may specify that the cutting or razing of the hill shall not cause any serious damage to any hill, building, structure, or land adjacent to or in the vicinity of the hill, obstruction to any drain, stream, or river, loss of life or property. The Act contains the permission procedure and criteria as well as specific provisions for punishment and legal actions against persons transgressing the law (Murshed, 2013). To prevent environmental degradation in the country, the Bangladesh Environmental Conservation Act 1995 was formulated. But the act contained no provision regarding illegal hill cutting. Later, in 2010, the Act was amended, giving additional power to the law enforcers. Nobody is allowed to cut trees

¹⁵ G. Kent, 'The human right to disaster mitigation and relief', 3 *Environmental Hazards* 137 (2001) at 137.

¹⁶ See the website of the UN International Strategy for Disaster Reduction, <http://www.unisdr.org/we/inform/terminology> (last accessed 26 November 2024).

¹⁷ <https://www.ohchr.org/en/treaty-bodies/ccpr/introduction-committee> (Accessed on 25 November 2025)

¹⁸ See cescr, Concluding Observations Dominican Republic, E/C.12/DOM/CO/3, 26 November 2010, para. 5.

¹⁹ See Human Rights Committee, General Comment No. 25 (The Right to Participate in Public Affairs) (1996), 'Compilation of General Comments and General Recommendations Adopted by Human Rights Treaty Bodies', HRI/GEN/1/ /Rev.7 (24 May 2004), para. 5

without prior permission from an authorized officer; otherwise, according to the law, they will be punished with 10 years' imprisonment or 10 lakh taka as monetary punishment or both.

Moreover, environmental mismanagement intensifies landslides. The disregard for existing legal instruments, such as the Bangladesh Environment Conservation Act 1995 and the Hill Management Rules 2015, indicates institutional weakness and inadequate coordination among relevant authorities (Mia et al., 2015). The destruction of natural vegetation and poor drainage infrastructure amplify the risks. Furthermore, women, children, and elderly persons remain the most affected due to vulnerability. The vulnerabilities to landslides in Chittagong are embedded in broader issues of governance, poverty, and ignorance of human rights. Addressing these vulnerabilities deserves an integrated policy approach that combines environmental protection with social justice.

Recommendations

Hills and hilly regions deserve special attention during the planning stage of development because they are considered ecologically and environmentally sensitive areas. It is a responsibility to conserve Chittagong's natural environment—the lack of planning interrupts the city's physical and environmental development. However, the hills should be safeguarded. Although excessive rainfall and hill cutting are considered the leading causes of landslides, the reasons why landslides occur are diverse. To reduce landslide vulnerability, forest cleaning on hills with steep slopes (more than 30°) should be halted, and more consultations should be held to develop green cover through tree planting on previously demolished hills. Proper engineering measures are needed to protect these demolished parts of the hills. The landslide tragedies in Chittagong city are examples of law enforcement failure. It is not only the insufficiency of law, but also the non-application or poor application of law, which destroys the hills and causes the death of hundreds of people in Chittagong. Therefore, strict law enforcement is not the only solution to address this situation. Strong implementation of laws can save the unique hills of Chittagong city.

Conclusion

Landslides in the Chittagong metropolitan area can be considered as socio-natural hazards. It requires sustained efforts to address landslide vulnerabilities, including poverty, social and humanitarian justice, communal violence, cultural differences, the upholding of human rights, the implementation of master/development plans and environmental laws, safeguarding institutional transparency, and promoting global peace and security. Nevertheless, to achieve overall success in landslide disaster risk reduction in Bangladesh, it is crucial to build a human rights-based disaster relief framework by enhancing research, policy-making, and planning. The marginalized and vulnerable community should be provided with adequate safeguards to address the challenges posed by landslides. Temporary and insufficient disaster relief should be replaced by sustainable, human rights-based relief.

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